

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TREATMENT OF CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA

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ABSTRACT

The course of inflammatory periodontal diseases is significantly complicated by iron deficiency anemia, and dental treatment becomes practically hopeless. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the immediate results of treatment of chronic catarrhal gingivitis against the background of iron deficiency anemia. The clinical study involved 63 patients aged 22–45 years. The effectiveness of periodontal treatment was determined based on the results of a visual and instrumental assessment of the condition of the gums, an index assessment of the condition of periodontal tissues, and an X-ray assessment of the condition of the alveolar bone. Sustained remission in patients with iron deficiency anemia is possible only after complex hematological treatment with iron supplements and supportive periodontal therapy.

Keywords: periodontium, hygiene, plaque, bleeding, catarrhal gingivitis, iron deficiency anemia.

Inflammatory periodontal diseases are highly prevalent and reach 85–90% of all dental diseases in patients over 30 years of age (Corraini P. et al., 2013). This is the most common cause of tooth loss due to a destructive process with the development of persistent dysfunction of the dental system (Yoshimura K. et al., 2012; Orekhova L. Yu. et al., 2016) and the appearance of foci of chronic infection in the oral cavity (Lakshev., 2011). Periodontal pathology is often combined with diseases of other body systems. Treatment of patients with a combination of inflammatory periodontal diseases and iron deficiency anemia becomes significantly more complicated. The prevalence in women of childbearing age reaches 30–60%. Unlike other types of anemia, patients with iron deficiency anemia develop not only anemic, but also sideropenic syndrome. Iron is part of not only hemoglobin, but also a number of enzyme systems in the body that provide tissue respiration and immune reactions (De Falco L. et al., 2014). Why is the course of inflammatory periodontal diseases significantly complicated by iron deficiency anemia, and dental treatment becomes practically hopeless? The pathogenetic mechanisms of this phenomenon remain poorly understood. Neutrophilic leukocytes have in their granularity components of antibacterial systems that contain iron and are dependent on its content in the body. These are primarily the myeloperoxidase and NADPH oxidase systems (Malam Z. et al., 2011; Hurst J.K., 2012; Larsen M.T. et al., 2013). The ineffectiveness of dental treatment of catarrhal gingivitis in patients with iron deficiency anemia is often due to profound dysfunction of neutrophil blood leukocytes due to inhibition of the iron-containing components of their antibacterial systems - myeloperoxidase and

NADPH oxidase. understanding the features of pathogenesis and, on this basis, clarifying the tactics of treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases in patients with iron deficiency anemia. The goal is to evaluate the immediate results of treatment of chronic catarrhal gingivitis against the background of iron deficiency anemia. Materials and methods of research The study involved 63 patients aged 22–45 years. The diagnosis of chronic catarrhal gingivitis (CHG) was established based on examination of the oral cavity, index assessment of periodontal tissue (OHI-S, PMA and CPITN) and orthopantomogram data. Group I included 24 patients with chronic hepatitis and normal hemoglobin levels in the blood, and group II included 21 patients with chronic hepatitis and iron deficiency anemia. The control group consisted of 18 healthy individuals without signs of periodontal disease. The diagnosis of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) was confirmed by hematological tests and laboratory parameters of iron, ferritin, and transferrin in the blood serum. When collecting anamnesis, the duration of remission, bad habits, occupational hazards and the presence of concomitant diseases were taken into account. For all patients, an individual scheme of hygienic and therapeutic and preventive measures was drawn up, taking into account the severity of gingivitis and the characteristics of the clinical course of the disease. We carried out complex local and general treatment together with therapists and hematologists. Etiotropic therapy was aimed at eliminating the microbial biofilm. To do this, the level of oral hygiene was determined using the “Plaque agent” rinse (Miradent). Dental plaque was removed using hand instruments, an ultrasonic scaler, and the Air-Flow air-abrasive system. Antiseptic treatment of the gums was carried out with 0.2% chlorhexidine bigluconate. The

necks of the teeth were coated with fluoride varnish "ClinPro White Varnish" (3M ESPE). We trained patients in the rules of individual oral hygiene and provided recommendations on the choice of hygiene products. During the treatment period, it was recommended to use a soft toothbrush with therapeutic and prophylactic toothpastes (Curaprox with chlorhexidine, Biorepair with lactoferin) and rinses, application of Metrogil-denta and Cholisal gels. old restorations with missing contact points, removed overhanging edges of fillings, removed low-quality orthopedic structures, and did selective grinding of teeth. Pathogenetic therapy included general and local anti-inflammatory treatment. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (1% emul-gel vol-taren) were used locally; steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (fluorocort, lorindene); antibacterial and antiseptic agents (gels "Cholisal", "Metrogil-denta", diplen films, 0.2% solution of chlorhexidine bigluconate, miramistin); enzyme preparations (trypsin, lidase, chymotrypsin); keratoplasty (dental solcoseryl). For systemic treatment, NSAIDs (butadione, voltaren, meloxicam), and, if necessary, antibiotics (amoxiclav, ciprofloxacin, azithromycin), antihistamines (claritin, loratidine, L-cet), and multivitamin complexes were prescribed. In patients of group I, a month after the start of treatment, a visual and instrumental assessment of the condition of periodontal tissues indicated signs of remission of CCH in 17 out of 24 patients (70.8%). Objectively, a decrease or absence of swelling and hyperemia of the gums was observed; the symptom of bleeding of the gums and grooves was negative. The PMA index decreased to $5.47 \pm 1.2\%$ (before treatment 40.6 ± 2.2). The level of oral hygiene improved significantly, there was practically no dental plaque, the hygiene index was 1.2 ± 0.05 points (before treatment 2.17 ± 0.03). In group II of the study, a month after the start of treatment, remission was observed in only 5 of 21 patients in this group (33.04%), even with a satisfactory level of hygiene, OHI-S = 1.2 ± 0.06 points (before treatment - 2, 14 ± 0.07 points). The patients complained of bleeding and pain in the cervical areas, swelling and hyperemia of the marginal edge and interdental papillae were pronounced, the PMA index was $49 \pm 0.4\%$ (before treatment $53.2 \pm 1.3\%$), which did not differ significantly from the initial examination. All patients of group II were treated together with hematologists. Two months later, a second course of local anti-inflammatory therapy was carried out and, if necessary, removal of dental plaque. When examined four months after the start of treatment with iron preparations, gingivitis remission was observed in 16 out of 21 patients (76.2%).

There was virtually no bleeding during probing, swelling and pain in the interdental papillae, marginal and alveolar gums, which was confirmed by a decrease in the PMA index to $11.32 \pm 0.2\%$.

Conclusions.

Treatment of chronic catarrhal gingivitis with a normal hemoglobin level according to a standard regimen has shown high effectiveness in achieving patients with a good level of oral hygiene. Sustained remission in patients with iron deficiency anemia is possible only after complex hematological treatment with iron supplements and supportive periodontal therapy.

References

1. Beltran-Aguilar E.D., Eke P.I., Thornton-Evans G. et al. Recording and surveillance systems for periodontal diseases // *Periodontology* 2000. – 2012. – Vol. 60, № 1. – P. 40–53.
2. Berlutti F., Pilloni A., Pietropaoli M. et al. Lactoferrin and oral diseases: current status and perspective in periodontitis // *Ann. Stomatol. (Roma)*. – 2011. – Vol. 2, No 3–4. – P. 10–18.
3. Chakraborty S., Tewari S., Sharma R.K. et al. Impact of iron deficiency anemia on chronic periodontitis and superoxide dismutase activity: a cross-sectional study // *J. Periodontal. Implant Sci.* – 2014. – Vol. 44, № 2. – P. 57–64.
4. Coad J., Pedley K. Iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia in women // *Scand. J. Clin. Lab. Invest. Suppl.* – 2014. – No 244. – P. 82–89.
5. Лит.: De Falco L., Sanchez M., Silvestri L. et al. Iron refractory iron deficiency anemia // *Haematologica*. – 2013. – Vol. 98. – No 6. – P. 845–853.
6. Enhos S., Duran I., Erdem S. et al. Relationship между ирон-дефицитной анемией и периодическим статусом в женщинах // *J. Periodontol.* – 2009. – Vol. 80. – No 11. – P. 1750–1755.
7. Laudénbach J.M., Simon Z. Common dental and periodontal diseases: evaluation and management // *Med. Clin. Северная Ам.* – 2014. – Vol. 98. – No 6. – P. 1239–1260.
8. O'Farrill-Santoscoy F., O'Farrill-Cadena M., Fragoso-Morales L.E. Evaluation of treatment of iron deficiency anemia in pregnancy // *Ginecol. Obstet. Mex.* – 2013. – Vol. 81. – No 7. – P. 377–381.
9. Powers J.M. & Buchanan G.R. Diagnosis and management of iron deficiency anemia // *Hematol. Oncol. Clin. Северная Ам.* – 2014. – Vol. 28. – No 4. – P. 729–745.
10. Rohani B. Oral manifestations and blood profile in patients with iron deficiency anemia // *J. Formos. Med. Assoc.* – 2015. – Vol. 114. – No 1.